

A Prospective Study on Functional Outcome at Donor Site Following Peroneus Longus Graft Harvest for Knee Ligament Reconstruction in a Tertiary Care Hospital in South India

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Abstract:

Background: Knee ligament reconstruction is widely performed all over the world and graft choice for the same has been always an area of research. Currently the most preferred grafts include the bone-patellar tendon-bone graft (BPTB) and the hamstring graft. However, there are some significant donor site morbidities associated with these grafts. Thus, we have used peroneus longus tendon as the graft which was found to have similar functional outcomes compared to hamstring graft and assessed functional outcome at the donor site associated with it.

Methods: Patients who required a knee ligament reconstruction were selected and Peroneus longus tendon was harvested as graft. The patients were followed up for 12 months post operatively. Functional scoring was done with AOFAS Ankle and Hindfoot scoring and Visual Analogue Scale - Foot and Ankle (VAS-FA) were used. Also, the power of foot eversion and plantar flexion was tested and recorded clinically by MRC grading.

Results: 30 patients fulfilled the inclusion criteria (22 male and 08 female patients). Follow up period was 12 months. The mean pre and postoperative AOFAS -AH score was 99.27 ± 0.94 and 99.13 ± 1.01 respectively at 12 months follow up. The mean pre and postoperative VAS-FA score was 98.53 ± 1.38 and 98.00 ± 1.34 respectively at 12 months follow up (p value > 0.05). The 12 months postoperative power of eversion and plantar flexion were grade 5 in all patients.

Conclusion: There was no significant difference of functional outcome and muscle power was noted postoperatively (at one year follow up) at the donor site following PLT graft harvest. Also, the surgical procedure of graft harvest was simple with less operative time with early wound healing and no complications postoperatively. Thus, we conclude that peroneus longus tendon can be used safely as a graft for ligament reconstruction with no significant donor site morbidities.

Keywords: Peroneus longus tendon Graft, ACL, AOFAS, VAS-AF.

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Introduction

Arthroscopic reconstruction of knee ligaments is one of the most commonly performed surgeries currently across the world. In India, it is observed that complete anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) tear constitutes nearly 6% of all knee injuries and 86% of sports related injuries.[1,2] Posterior cruciate ligaments (PCL) tears were found to be less in incidence, but almost 96.5% of these injuries had an additional ligament injury, mostly ACL.[3]

The selection of grafts for ligament reconstruction is an area where extensive research is conducted. One of the characteristics that surgeons look for in an ideal graft is the donor site morbidity associated with its harvest.(4) Currently the most commonly

preferred grafts for ligament reconstruction are bone-patellar tendon-bone graft (BPTB) and hamstring grafts.[4,5] However, there are some significant donor site morbidities associated with BPTB graft which include anterior knee pain, discomfort on kneeling, patellar fracture, patellar tendon rupture and contracture.[6] Hamstring harvesting can cause damage to the saphenous nerve[7], it can cause instability in cases of ACL with MCL grade 3 injury[8], risk of residual muscle tearing, decreased flexion strength, and decreased internal rotation strength.[9]

Thus, considering the various significant donor site morbidities associated with the most commonly

used grafts, a different graft which is being used is the Peroneus Longus tendon (PLT) graft. Peroneus longus autograft was found to have functional outcomes similar to hamstring graft and larger graft diameter compared to hamstring graft.[10,11] There has been studies which evaluated the donor site morbidities and functional outcomes and have concluded that peroneus longus could not be recommended as a first option for ACL reconstruction due to decreased power of eversion and first ray plantarflexion and ankle instability.[12] Also there has been studies concluding there was excellent functional outcomes and no significant donor site morbidities associated with peroneus longus graft harvest.[13] In this study we would like to evaluate the functional outcome at the donor site following peroneus longus graft harvest for knee ligament reconstruction.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Prospective Study Design

Study Setting: Study conducted at the Department of Orthopedics in Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Bangalore and its attached hospitals.

Study Duration: 15 months (August 2022 to November 2023)

Study Population: Patients aged between 18-40 years who were diagnosed with ACL or PCL injury clinically as well as confirmed by MRI scan were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients from both the sexes aged between 18-40 years who were diagnosed with ACL or PCL injury clinically as well as confirmed by MRI scan who were willing to participate in the study were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who had any pre-existing ankle or foot deformity and patients who had any pre-existing ankle or foot morbidity as evidenced by preop American Orthopedic Foot and Ankle Society (AOFAS) Ankle-hindfoot Score [14] less than 95 and Visual Analogue Scale - Foot and Ankle (VAS-FA) [15] less than 95 were excluded.

Sample Size: A total 30 patients were included in the study during the study period.

Sampling Method: Purposive Sampling Method

Data Collection Method and Follow Up: After obtaining the permission from Institutional Ethics Committee and taking written informed consent from the participants the data collection was started. The data was collected using a pre-structured clinical proforma consisting of basic demographic details, history and clinical examination along with AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot score and VAS-FA scale.

AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot score is having a maximum score of 100 across three parameters: Pain-40 points, Function- 50 points and Alignment-10 points.[14] VAS-FA Scale ranges from 0-100.

The participants underwent a preoperative evaluation of ankle function with AOFAS (American orthopedic foot and ankle society Ankle-hindfoot score) and VAS-FA (Visual analogue scale - foot and ankle). Also, the muscle power of eversion and plantarflexion by Medical Research Council (MRC) Scale for Muscle Strength was used and after this patient was taken for surgery.

Surgical Procedure: The patient was positioned supine under spinal anesthesia. After arthroscopic confirmation of ACL/PCL tear the graft harvest was started from the ipsilateral Peroneus Longus Tendon (PLT). A skin incision of 2 cm made posterior to the lateral malleoli. After subcutaneous dissection, the PLT was identified. The PLT lies slightly posterior and superior to the peroneus brevis tendon (PBT) at this area. Care was taken not to injure the sural nerve while dissecting. Whipstitches are applied on two ends and tendon cut in between. A closed tendon stripper was used to strip the tendon at musculotendinous junction taking care to avoid injury to the common peroneal nerve. The remaining distal portion of the tendon is sutured onto the PBT. The graft is prepared, tripled and loaded onto a loop. The subcutaneous tissue closed with vicryl and skin closed with staples. Then the surgeon carried on with the ligament reconstruction.

Postoperatively, staples were removed at 2 weeks and standard rehabilitation protocol was followed. Patients were evaluated at 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months and 1 year postoperatively. In each visit, the AOFAS Ankle and Hindfoot scoring, VAS-FA scoring and the MRC power grading of eversion and plantar flexion was recorded.

Statistical Analysis: The data were be entered in Microsoft excel and analyzed using EpiInfo software. The data were analyzed in the form frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, median and interquartile range. The mean preoperative and postoperative values for AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot score, VAS-FA and MRC power grading were compared using paired t test and a p value of less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 30 participants were included in our study, among which 22 (73.3%) were males and 8 (26.7%) were female patients with a mean age of 27.8 ± 4.2 years. Among these 28 (93.3%) were ACL reconstructions and 2 (6.7%) were PCL reconstructions. The reasons for injury were fall or

minor injury 24 (80%), fall while playing sports 4 (13.3%) and road traffic accident 2 (6.7%). (Table1)

Table 1: Basic Demographic and Clinical Details of the participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
• Male	22	73.3
• Female	08	26.7
Age Group		
• 18-30 years	17	56.7
• 31-40 years	13	43.3
Cause of Injury		
• Fall or Minor injury	24	80.0
• Fall during sports	04	13.3
• Road traffic accidents	02	06.7
Reconstructed Ligament		
• Anterior Cruciate Ligament	28	93.3
• Posterior Cruciate Ligament	02	06.7

We followed up the patients at 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months. The results at 12 months were used for the final assessment. The preoperative mean AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot score was 100 ± 0 and postoperative score at 12 months follow up was 98.7 ± 1.5 at the donor site. The

preoperative mean VAS-FA was 98.5 ± 1.4 and postoperative score at 12 months follow up was 98.00 ± 1.3 at the donor site. (Table 2). The mean MRC power grading of eversion and plantarflexion at donor site during preoperative and postoperative at 1 year follow up was 5.

Chart 1: Mean Preoperative and follow up AOFAS-AH and VAS-FA Score of the participants

Table 2: Preoperative and Follow up Scores of AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot (AOFAS-AH) and VAS-FA Score of the participants at the donor site

Time	AOFAS-AH Score Mean (SD)	VAS-FA Score Mean (SD)
Preoperative	99.27 (0.94)	98.5 (1.4)
6 Weeks follow up	88.5 (3.4)	89.5 (3.5)
3 Months follow up	95.4 (2.6)	95.3 (2.4)
6 Months follow up	98.3 (1.8)	97.5 (1.3)
One Year follow up	99.13 (1.01)	98.0 (1.3)

The AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot score comparison for functional outcome at the donor site before and after surgery (one year follow up) using Paired ‘t’ test was 0.1033 and it was statistically not significant and similarly VAS-FA score was also not statistically significant before and after surgery (one year follow up). (Table 3). Also, the MRC

power grading of eversion and plantarflexion were restored to grade 5 in all patients at 12 months. The wound healing was normal in all patients with no surgical site infection in any of the patients at the donor site.

There were no neurological complications noted in any of the patients in the study.

Table 3: Preoperative and one year follow-up comparison of AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot (AOFAS-AH) and VAS-FA Score of the participants at the donor site

Scoring System	Mean ± SD	P value
AOFAS Ankle-hindfoot Score		
• Preoperative	99.27 ± 0.94	0.1033
• One year follow-up	99.13 ± 1.01	
VAS-FA Score		
• Preoperative	98.5 ± 1.4	0.054
• One year follow-up	98.0 ± 1.3	

Discussion:

The graft choice for knee ligament reconstruction has always been an area of intense debate. Although there is no such thing as an ideal graft, there are certain properties of the graft which we look into while choosing the graft. One among them is that there should be no or very minimal donor site morbidity. There are significant donor site morbidities associated with the two most common grafts used i.e., hamstring graft and BPTB grafts which have been reported in previous studies.[4-9]

Our study was conducted with the aim to evaluate the possible donor site morbidities that can occur with a peroneus longus tendon autograft. Here in this study, we have used two scoring systems. One is AOFAS hindfoot and ankle scoring which includes the pain, function and alignment as its components. The other one is Visual analogue scale - Foot and Ankle which is more of a subjective

scoring by the patient. In both these scoring systems, comparing the preop and postop 12 months values, we find that there were no significant differences in both and indicating that one of the good choices to use PLT for ACL or PCL repair which was similar to other studies.[10-13, 17]

Also, the MRC power grading was done for eversion and plantarflexion which are the two main action of the PL, and the 12 months postoperative evaluation showed that all patients had a grade 5 power in both these actions. The eversion is also carried out by peroneus brevis which may take up the action of PLT and the plantarflexion is also carried out by other muscles like tibialis posterior. Also there has been evidence in MRI studies that showed regeneration of PLT.[17]

Here, we have used only clinical methods to evaluate the function and power and not any advanced techniques or tools, since none of our

patients were high demand individuals like professional athletes or dancers. A satisfactory functional score and a grade 4 or 5 power was adequate for our group of patients to be considered as a great result.

The operative procedure was found to be quick, simple and straightforward, with our average time for graft harvest being 7-10 minutes skin to skin. There was no wound complications noted in our group with all patients showing excellent wound healing. There were no neurological complications noted in any of the patients. The expected nerve injuries are common peroneal nerve which can be injured while stripping the tendon which can be protected by not passing the stripper above the level. Another one is sural nerve which comes more posterior to the PLT and can be protected while dissecting.

The limitations of our study, we have used only clinical evaluation and functional scoring, and though it can be applicable to most of the general population, it cannot be extrapolated to high demand individuals like professional athletes or dancers whom we have not included in the study. Also, the followup period is only 12 months and the long-term outcomes need to be evaluated by carrying out longer studies.

Conclusion:

There was no significant difference of functional outcome and muscle power was noted postoperatively (at one year follow up) at the donor site following PLT graft harvest. Also, the surgical procedure of graft harvest was simple with less operative time with early wound healing and no complications postoperatively. Thus, we conclude that peroneus longus tendon can be used safely as a graft for ligament reconstruction with no significant donor site morbidities.

References:

- Gera SK, Pilar A, Saji MJ, Amaravathi RS. Epidemiology of Anterior Cruciate Ligament Injuries – A Hospital-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Karnataka Orthopaedic Association*, January- February 2021; 9(1): 30-35.
- John R, Dhillon MS, Syam K, Prabhakar S, Behera P, Singh H. Epidemiological profile of sports-related knee injuries in northern India: An observational study at a tertiary care centre. *J Clin Orthop Trauma*. 2016; 7(3):207–11.
- Ganelli GC, Edson CJ. PCL injuries in trauma patients: part 2 *Arthroscopy*.1995; 11(5):526-529
- Robert H. Miller III, Frederick M Azar. Knee Injuries. In: Frederick M Azar, James H Beatty, editors. *Campbell's Operative Orthopaedics*. 14th Ed Vol III p. 2282-2310
- Tibor L, Chan PH, Funabashi TT, et al. Surgical technique trends in primary ACL reconstruction for 2007-2014. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 2016; 98-A(13): 1079-1089
- Kartor J, Movin T, Karlsson J. Donor site morbidity and anterior knee problems after ACL reconstruction using autografts. *Arthroscopy* 2009;17: 971-80
- Nelissen E, Van Arkel ER, Hazelberg HM. Traumatic neuroma of the infrapatellar branch of saphenous nerve after hamstring harvesting. *J knee Surg* 2010;23(04):233-36
- Ahn JH, Lee SH. Risk factors for knee instability after ACL reconstruction. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc* 2016; 24(09):2936-2942
- Thomas AC, Villwock M, Wojtys EM, Palmier Smith RM (2013) Lower extremity muscle strength after ACL injury and reconstruction. *J Athl Train* 48(5):610-620
- Rhatomy S., Askin,A.I.Z., Wardani, A.E., et al. Peroneus longus autograft can be recommended as a superior graft to hamstring tendon in single bundle ACL reconstruction. *Knee Surg sports traumatol arthrosc* 27,3552-3559 (2019)
- Goyal, T., Paul, S., Choudhury, A.K. et al. Full-thickness peroneus longus tendon autograft for anterior cruciate reconstruction in multi-ligament injury and revision cases: outcomes and donor site morbidity. *Eur J Orthop Surg Traumatol* 33, 21–27 (2023)
- Angthong C, Chernchujit B, Apivatgaroon A, Chaijenkit K, Nualon P, Suchao-In K. The anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction with the peroneus longus tendon: a biomechanical and clinical evaluation of the donor ankle morbidity. *J Med Assoc Thai*. 2015 Jun 1; 98(6):555-60.
- Rhatomy S, Hartoko L, Setyawan R, Soekarno NR, Asikin AI, Pridianto D, Mustamsir E. Single bundle ACL reconstruction with peroneus longus tendon graft: 2-years follow-up. *Journal of clinical orthopaedics and trauma*. 2020 May 1;11:S332-6
- de Boer AS, Tjioe RJC, Van der Sijde F, Meuffels DE, den Hoed PT, Van der Vlies CH, Tuinebreijer WE, Verhofstad MHJ, Van Lieshout EMM; AOFAS Study Group. The American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society Ankle-Hindfoot Scale; translation and validation of the Dutch language version for ankle fractures. *BMJ Open*. 2017 Aug 3; 7(8):e017040.
- Stüber J, Zech S, Bay R, Qazzaz A, Richter M. Normative data of the Visual Analogue Scale Foot and Ankle (VAS FA) for pathological conditions. *Foot Ankle Surg*. 2011 Sep; 17(3):166-72.

16. Kleyweg RP, van der Meche FGA, Schmitz PIM., Interobserver agreement in the assessment of muscle strength and functional abilities in Guillain-Barré syndrome. *Muscle Nerve*.1991 Nov; 14 (11): 1103-1109.
17. Shao X, Shi LL, Bluman EM, Wang S, Xu X, Chen X, et al. Satisfactory functional and MRI outcomes at the foot and ankle following harvesting of full thickness peroneus longus tendon graft. *Bone Joint J*. 2020 Feb 1; 102-B (2):205-211.